

Evaluation of Asymmetric Dimethylarginine (ADMA) levels of Diabetic -Hypertensive Comorbidity Subjects in Bayelsa State

Edesemi R. Murray^{1*}, Adline E. Ben-Chioma², & Helen A. Waribo²

¹ Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

² Department of Clinical Chemistry, Faculty of Medical Laboratory Science, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Corresponding author's email/Phone number: rebecca.murray@rsu.edu.ng
+2348144643351

Article type: Original

Cite as: Murray ER, Ben-Chioma AE, Waribo HA. Evaluation of Asymmetric Dimethylarginine (ADMA) levels of Diabetic -Hypertensive Comorbidity Subjects in Bayelsa State. *Nexus Med. Lab. Sci. J.* 2026;3(1):1-11

Received on 22nd January, 2026; Accepted on 26th February, 2026; Published on 28th February, 2026

Publisher: ScholarlyFeed

<https://doi.org/10.71462/sfpl2601001>

ABSTRACT

Background: Diabetes mellitus is responsible for approximately 1.5 million deaths globally according to the World Health Organization. The existence of hypertension with diabetes serves as a critical risk factor for the progression of chronic diabetic complications, significantly amplifying morbidity and mortality rates. Despite its clinical significance, the role of asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), remains under explored in individuals with diabetes-hypertension comorbidity. **Objective:** This study aims to evaluate the ADMA levels in subjects with coexisting diabetes and hypertension in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. **Methods:** An analytical cross-sectional study was adopted involving 200 participants aged 18–70 years attending diabetic and cardiovascular clinics at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, and Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The participants were randomly recruited and grouped into four categories with an oral consent: apparently healthy controls (n=50), diabetes mellitus (DM) subjects (n=50), hypertensive (HTN) subjects (n=50), and those with coexisting hypertension and diabetes (HTN/DM; n=50). Venous blood samples were collected for the analysis of ADMA using ELISA method. Some demographic parameters were collected from the structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism Version 9.0.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The study revealed significantly elevated ADMA levels in HTN and HTN/DM groups compared to DM and control groups ($p = 0.007$). Males had a higher prevalence for hypertension than females. The middle age range of 30-49 populated the study. **Conclusion:** These findings suggest that coexisting diabetes and hypertension synergistically increases ADMA levels which might potentially increase cardiovascular risk. The need for early routine diagnosis of ADMA, identification of at-risk groups, monitoring, and targeted intervention strategies could mitigate cardiovascular complications in subjects with diabetes-hypertension comorbidity.

Keywords: *Asymmetric Dimethylarginine, Diabetes, Hypertensive, Comorbidity, Yenagoa*

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes accounts for about 1.5 million deaths worldwide [1]. As of 2021, an estimated 537 million people had diabetes worldwide accounting for 10.5% of the adult population, with type 2 making up about 90% of all cases. The prevalence of the disease continues to increase, most dramatically in low- and middle-income nations including Nigeria [2]. Studies have shown that hypertension is a major risk factor for the development and progression of chronic diabetic complications and both conditions are comorbidities [3]. Although diabetes mellitus is associated with a considerably increased cardiovascular risk, the presence of hypertension in the diabetic individual markedly increases morbidity and mortality [4]. Data has shown that hypertension has been implicated in 44% of deaths attributed to diabetes, and diabetes is involved in 10% of deaths attributed to hypertension [5,6]. The development of hypertension in diabetic individuals not only complicates treatment strategies and increases healthcare costs but also heightens the risk for macrovascular and microvascular complications considerably [7].

Nitric oxide (NO), which is synthesized by NO synthases has been identified as an important antiatherogenic molecule [8]. As initially described by Vallance *et al.* [9], as an endogenous inhibitor of NO synthase. On the other hand, asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), occurs in significant amounts in peripheral blood as a naturally occurring chemical found in blood plasma and a metabolic by-product of continual protein modification processes in the cytoplasm of all human cells. It is characterized as a circulating endogenous inhibitor of nitric oxide (NO) synthase by competing with L-arginine as the substrate [8]. Moreover, ADMA may increase oxidative stress by uncoupling the electron

transport between NO synthase and L-arginine, which can lead to decrease in the production and availability of endothelium-derived nitric oxide [10]. Therefore, derangement of the L-arginine- NO pathway and increase of oxidative stress by ADMA have been implicated as important contributing factors for the development of endothelial dysfunction and, by extension, cardiovascular health [11].

Since this discovery, multiple clinical studies have linked elevated circulating ADMA concentrations with increased cardiovascular risk. Studies suggest ADMA as an independent predictor of cardiovascular morbidity [12,13]. In type 2 diabetes patients, cross-sectional studies have associated ADMA with macrovascular and microvascular diabetic complications and disease [14,15], and increased ADMA levels have been observed in insulin resistance, both in type 1 and type 2 diabetes [15].

Despite these findings, the predictive role of ADMA in cardiovascular events among patients with diabetes-hypertension comorbidity in Bayelsa State Nigeria remains unexplored. Therefore, evaluating ADMA levels could facilitate the early identification of high-risk individuals, improving disease management, preventing severe complications, and reducing mortality rates.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Design

This is an analytical cross-sectional study comprising of 4 groups; 1 is apparently healthy subjects without diabetes, hypertension or diabetes and hypertension comorbidity, 2- Subjects with diabetes without hypertension, 3- Subjects with hypertension

without diabetes, while the 4th group subjects were of diabetic-hypertensive comorbidity all residing in Bayelsa State either attending NDUTH Okolobiri and FMC Yenagoa.

2.2 Study Area

The study was conducted at Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH), Okolobiri, Yenagoa LGA, Bayelsa State, Nigeria and Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital is located at Okolobiri; Okolobiri is a community in Gbarain-Ekpetiama in Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Yenagoa is the capital of Bayelsa State and one of the eight (8) Local Government Areas of the state. Bayelsa state shares boundaries with Delta State on the North, Rivers State on the East and the Atlantic Ocean on the West and South. Yenagoa is geographically located within longitude 50 15 E and 60 45 E and the latitude is 40 45N and 50 23 S. It has an area of 945 km² and a population of 353,304 persons in the 2006 census. The NDUTH Okolobiri established in September 2007 and the FMC Yenagoa established in 1999, both offers tertiary health services, train healthcare manpower and conduct health research.

2.3 Study Population

A total of 200 subjects comprising of male and female adults between the ages of 30 to 69 years were recruited for the study. Fifty (50) subjects were confirmed diabetics, another Fifty (50) subjects were confirmed hypertensives, fifty (50) other subjects exhibited a diabetic -hypertensive comorbidity while the remaining Fifty (50) subjects which were apparently healthy served as the control. They were informed about the study, and oral consent was obtained from interested participants. A well-

structured questionnaire was administered to gather relevant information

2.4 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study was determined using G*Power statistical software. The F-test family with a One-Way ANOVA design was selected with further parameters set as follows:

Effect size (f) = 0.30, Power (1 – β err prob) = 0.95. α error probability = 0.05, Number of groups = 4. This yielded a sample size of 196. However, to enhance the statistical robustness and allow for potential data loss, the sample size was increased to 200, with 50 subjects assigned to each group in the study.

2.5 Inclusion Criteria

Participants who met the following criteria were recruited; Male and female adults within the age range of 18–60 years, confirmed diabetics attending the diabetic clinic with a fasting blood glucose above 10mmol/L and HbA1c > 6.5%, confirmed Hypertensive patients with blood pressure readings of over 150/90mmHg, these Diabetic and hypertensive patients were currently attending diabetic and cardiovascular clinic in Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH), Okolobiri, Bayelsa State, Nigeria and /or FMC Yenagoa, and those willing to give informed consent to participate in the study.

2.6 Exclusion Criteria

Subjects who did not give informed consent, are alcoholics, suffering from any other coronary heart disease or on any form of medications were excluded from the study.

2.7 Ethical Considerations

The ethical clearance was gotten from the ethical committee of Federal Medical Centre,

Yenagoa (FMCY/REC/ECC/2024/AUG/776) and Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital (NDUTH), Okolobiri, Bayelsa State (NDUTH/REC/0078/2024).

2.8 Sample Collection, Transportation, Processing and Preservation

Five (5) ml of blood sample was collected with the use of vacutainer plain tube for ADMA analysis. This was allowed to clot, then the clotted samples were spun using a centrifuge (NewLife bucket centrifuge, Model: 800D) at 3000rpm for 5minutes. The serum was collected into another plain bottle and properly labeled for ADMA analysis. The processed samples were preserved using ice pack in a thermo-cool container at a temperature of 2°C - 8°C and then transported to the laboratory where they were analyzed.

2.9 Estimation of Serum ADMA

Human ADMA ELISA Kit by Bioassay Technology Laboratory were used. The concentration of ADMA in the samples was determined using the Sandwich ELISA Method as described by Enfrall and Perlmann [16].

2.10 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was computed using GraphPad Prism Software Version 9.0.0 (121),

San Diego, CA. Data obtained from this study were presented as mean \pm SD. Statistical comparison between groups were done using one-way ANOVA, while Tukey's multiple comparison (Post Hoc tests) was used to obtain specific significant differences among the various groups. Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1: Demographic Details of Subjects

The demographic characteristics of the study subjects revealed that hypertensive subjects had 27 males (54%) and 23 females (46%), while the hypertensive/diabetic (HTN/DM) group comprised 25 males (50%) and 25 females (50%). Similarly, diabetic subjects were equally distributed between males (50%) and females (50%), whereas the apparently healthy control group had more males (30; 60%) than females (20; 40%). For age distribution, the majority of subjects in all groups were within the 30–49 years age range, 35 (70%) hypertensive, 33 (66%) HTN/DM, 36 (72%) diabetic, and 33 (66%) control subjects. The remaining subjects were aged 50–69 years, accounting for 15 (30%) hypertensive, 17 (34%) HTN/DM, 14 (28%) diabetic, and 17 (34%) control subjects (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Detail of Subjects

Variables	Hypertensive Subjects	Hypertensive/ Diabetic Subjects	Diabetic Subjects	Apparently Healthy Control Subjects
Sex				
Male	27 (54%)	25 (50%)	25 (50%)	30 (60%)
Female	23 (46%)	25 (50%)	25 (50%)	20 (40%)
Age Range (Years)				
30 – 49	35 (70%)	33 (66%)	36 (72%)	33 (66%)
50 – 69	15 (30%)	17 (34%)	14 (28%)	17 (34%)

3.2: Comparison of Mean Levels of ADMA among the Study Subjects

There was a significant increase in the mean levels of ADMA in hypertensive (0.60 ± 0.23 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) and hypertensive/diabetic (0.65 ± 0.33 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects compared to the control (0.53 ± 0.23 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects ($p = 0.007$). The mean ADMA levels of the diabetic subjects (0.49 ± 0.21 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) were not significantly different from that of the control (0.53 ± 0.23 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects. There was a significant

increase in the mean levels of ADMA when hypertensive/diabetic (0.65 ± 0.33 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects were compared with diabetic (0.49 ± 0.21 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects ($p = 0.007$). However, the mean levels of ADMA in hypertensive/diabetic (0.65 ± 0.33 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects were not significantly different from that of the hypertensive (0.60 ± 0.23 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) subjects (Table 2).

Table 2: Mean \pm SD of ADMA Levels among the Study Subjects

Groups	ADMA ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)
HTN (n=50)	0.60 ± 0.23^a
DM (n=50)	0.49 ± 0.21^b
HTN/DM (n=50)	0.65 ± 0.33^a
Control (n=50)	0.53 ± 0.23^b
F-value	4.11
P-value	0.007
Remark	S

Keys: Values in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different from each other ($p \leq 0.05$). HTN-Hypertension subjects, DM-Diabetes mellitus subjects, HTN/DM-Subjects with the two conditions, ADMA - Asymmetric Dimethylarginine

The result shows that the hypertensive/diabetic comorbidity group had the highest mean levels of systolic pressure and diastolic pressure ($156.06 \pm 13.18\text{mmHg}$ / $90.34 \pm 22.64\text{mmHg}$). This was followed by the hypertensive group (155.86 ± 12.53 / $83.14 \pm 14.92\text{mmHg}$) compared to the control (121.76 ± 3.46 / $75.13 \pm 9.80\text{mmHg}$) as reflected in the Table 3.

3.3: Comparison of Mean Levels of Blood Pressure among the Study Subjects

Table 3: Mean \pm SD of Blood Pressure levels in the Study Subjects

Groups	DP (mmHg)	SP (mmHg)
HTN (n=50)	83.14 ± 14.92^a	155.86 ± 12.53^a
DM (n=50)	85.11 ± 11.79^a	125.42 ± 5.56^b
HTN/DM (n=50)	90.34 ± 22.64^b	156.06 ± 13.18^a
Control (n=50)	75.13 ± 9.80^c	121.76 ± 3.46^c
F-value	8.212	188.199
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001
Remark	S	S

Keys: Values in the same row but having different superscripts are significantly

different from each other ($p \leq 0.05$). HTN-Hypertension subjects, DM-Diabetes mellitus

subjects, HTN/DM-Subjects with the two conditions, SP-Systolic Pressure, DP-Diastolic Pressure

3.4: Comparison of Mean Levels of Glycemic Parameters among the Study Groups

The mean levels of fasting blood sugar (FBS) and glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) among the study subjects revealed that there was a significant increase in both FBS and HbA1c

levels in diabetic (8.92 ± 1.47 mmol/L; $6.96 \pm 0.58\%$) and hypertensive/diabetic (9.50 ± 1.95 mmol/L; $7.09 \pm 0.66\%$) subjects compared to the control (4.34 ± 0.38 mmol/L; $4.68 \pm 0.47\%$) subjects ($p < 0.0001$). The hypertensive subjects had lower FBS and HbA1c (4.40 ± 0.58 mmol/L; $4.55 \pm 0.72\%$). Conversely, these mean levels of FBS and HbA1c in hypertensive subjects were not significantly different from those of the control subjects (4.34 ± 0.38 mmol/L; $4.68 \pm 0.47\%$). (Table 4).

Table 4: Mean \pm SD of Glycemic Parameters among Study Groups

Groups	FBS (mmol/L)	HbA1c (%)
HTN (n=50)	4.40 ± 0.58^a	4.55 ± 0.72^a
DM (n=50)	8.92 ± 1.47^b	6.96 ± 0.58^b
HTN/DM (n=50)	9.50 ± 1.95^b	7.09 ± 0.66^b
Control (n=50)	4.34 ± 0.38^a	4.68 ± 0.47^a
F-value	244.63	256.62
P-value	<0.0001	<0.0001
Remark	S	S

Keys: Values in the same row but having different superscripts are significantly different from each other ($p \leq 0.05$). HTN-Hypertensive subjects, DM-Diabetes mellitus subjects, HTN/DM-Subjects with the two conditions, FBS – Fasting Blood Sugar, HbA1c – Glycated Haemoglobin

4. DISCUSSION

From the demographic results, men tend to have a higher percentage of Hypertension than the female. This aligns with studies of Fryar et al [17]. The reason for this observation might be attributed to behavior, biological and life style factors. A systemic review by Adeloye et al [18] also aligned with men having a higher pool in percentage of hypertension than

females however, some studies indicate gender disparities [19]. Furthermore, hypertension has been stated to occur within the middle age adult [17]. This is in line with the observations in this study where a higher percentage in the middle age brackets of the hypertensive group was seen (Table 1).

From this study, there was a significant increase in ADMA levels in the hypertensive group compared to the control group (Table 2). This elevation in ADMA reflects marked endothelial dysfunction. The increased systolic and diastolic levels might have also compromised the metabolic state since it is noted that ADMA is an endogenous competitive inhibitor of nitric oxide synthase (NOS), the enzyme responsible for converting L-arginine to nitric oxide (NO) - a potent

vasodilator and key regulator of vascular tone and endothelial health [20]. When ADMA levels rise, NO synthesis is inhibited, leading to reduced nitric oxide bioavailability. On the other hand, decline in nitric oxide impairs vascular relaxation, promotes vasoconstriction, and increases systemic vascular resistance, thereby could be a contributing factor which might have directly elevated blood pressure as observed in this study [21].

Hypertension promotes a pro-oxidative and pro-inflammatory vascular environment [22]. The increased ADMA observed in the subjects under study might have also resulted from oxidative stress build up in the system because of the metabolic pathologies from the diseases. Oxidative stress generates excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS), which not only degrade nitric oxide but also inhibit the enzyme dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase (DDAH), the primary enzyme responsible for metabolizing and clearing ADMA. So, when DDAH activity is suppressed, ADMA accumulates within endothelial cells and the circulation [23]. Moreover, inflammatory cytokines are often elevated in hypertensive states, which might have further downregulate DDAH expression and enhance ADMA production through increased methylation of arginine residues in proteins by protein arginine methyltransferases (PRMTs) [21, 22]. In addition, the mechanical stress exerted on the vascular wall due to persistently elevated blood pressure causes endothelial injury and dysfunction, triggering the release of ADMA into the bloodstream [24]. These combined mechanisms (reduced ADMA degradation, enhanced production, and endothelial damage), synergistically contribute to the observed rise in ADMA levels among hypertensive subjects. Therefore, the significant elevation of ADMA in this study is

consistent with the pathophysiological basis of hypertension, where nitric oxide deficiency, oxidative stress, and inflammation converge to promote vascular dysfunction in hypertensive individuals [13, 25]. This finding aligns with previous studies by Dowsett *et al* [25] and Mittermayer *et al.* [13] who reported significantly higher plasma ADMA concentrations in essential hypertension.

There was no significant difference in ADMA levels in the diabetic groups compared to the control group (Table 2). The absence of a significant difference in ADMA levels among diabetic participants and control may be attributed to the influence of several biological and clinical factors known to modulate ADMA metabolism and endothelial function, including disease duration, level of metabolic control, and exposure to pharmacologic therapy. Although treatment adherence was not formally assessed, the fact that many participants were already receiving antidiabetic medications suggests a possible, contribution to limiting the degree of endothelial dysfunction typically associated with poorly controlled or long-standing diabetes. Also, compensatory mechanisms such as enhanced dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase (DDAH) activity, improved antioxidant defenses, and the effects of commonly prescribed agents (e.g., metformin, ACE inhibitors, or statins) may mitigate ADMA accumulation by enhancing nitric oxide bioavailability and reducing oxidative stress [26]. In the hypertensive group, the expected ADMA-lowering benefit of ACE inhibitors may not have been evident because not all patients with hypertension are necessarily treated with this drug class, as management often involves diverse antihypertensive regimens with varying effects on endothelial function. This observation aligns with the findings of

Sciacqua et al. [27], who also reported no significant difference in ADMA concentrations between patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and controls.

ADMA levels were highest in the HTN/DM group compared to both hypertensive and diabetic groups (Table 2), indicating a synergistic effect of hypertension and diabetes on endothelial dysfunction. The coexistence of hyperglycemia and elevated blood pressure amplifies oxidative stress and suppresses DDAH activity, leading to pronounced ADMA accumulation [28]. Note that hyperglycemia-induced advanced glycation end products (AGEs) and hypertension-driven vascular wall stress jointly enhance oxidative and inflammatory signaling, perpetuating nitric oxide deficiency and vascular remodeling [29]. Both diseases share convergent pathogenic mechanisms that culminate in endothelial dysfunction [30]. In diabetes, chronic hyperglycemia increases ROS through mitochondrial overactivity and NADPH oxidase activation, leading to oxidative stress, L-arginine oxidation, and endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) inhibition, while simultaneously elevating ADMA, an endogenous eNOS inhibitor [31,32]. In hypertension, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) elevates angiotensin II, which stimulates NADPH oxidase, increases superoxide production, and further depletes nitric oxide [33]. When both diseases coexist, insulin resistance augments free fatty acid flux and the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6, intensifying oxidative stress and endothelial injury [34]. Chronic inflammation further inhibits DDAH, impeding ADMA degradation and facilitating its accumulation [29]. Consequently, persistent oxidative stress, impaired insulin signaling, and inflammation act synergistically in

HTN/DM comorbidity to elevate ADMA levels and aggravate vascular dysfunction beyond the effects of either disease alone [35]. This finding aligns with reports by Sibal *et al.* [21] and Mwende [36], who observed significantly higher ADMA concentrations in patients with both conditions than in those with either alone. These findings also align with reports by Chen *et al.* [37], who observed strong associations between elevated ADMA, endothelial dysfunction, and cardiovascular risk.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings suggest metabolic imbalance, endothelial dysfunction and a potential cardiovascular risk when hypertension coexists with diabetes mellitus in subjects as reflected in the elevated asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) levels observed in hypertensive and comorbid hypertensive/diabetic subjects. This highlights the critical need for early diagnosis and identification of at-risk individuals. Also, integration of management strategies to cater for patients with comorbidity in order to reduce cardiovascular burden and avert long-term health outcomes.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors declared that no competing interests exist.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Author ERM managed the literature searches and analysis. Author AEB wrote the protocol. Author HAW designed the study and wrote the first draft. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Hypertension [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 May 22]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hypertension>.
2. De Silva AP, De Silva SH, Haniffa R, Liyanage IK, Jayasinghe S, Katulanda P. Inequalities in the prevalence of diabetes mellitus and its risk factors in Sri Lanka: a lower middle-income country. *Int J Equity Health*. 2018;17(1):45–56.
3. Petrie JR, Guzik TJ, Touyz RM. Diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease: clinical insights and vascular mechanisms. *Can J Cardiol*. 2018;34(5):575–584.
4. Tsimihodimos V, Gonzalez-Villalpando C, Meigs JB, Ferrannini E. Hypertension and diabetes mellitus: coprediction and time trajectories. *Hypertension*. 2018;71(3):422–428.
5. Epstein M, Sowers JR. Diabetes mellitus and hypertension. *Hypertension*. 1992;19(5):403–418.
6. Fasehun OO, Adjei-Mensah J, Ugorji WS, Titus VO, Asade OO, Adeyemo DA, et al. Trends and patterns in hypertension-related deaths: a comprehensive analysis using CDC WONDER data. *Cureus*. 2024;16(10):70754–70759.
7. Perreault L, Pan Q, Aroda VR, Barrett-Connor E, Dabelea D, Dagogo-Jack S, et al. Exploring residual risk for diabetes and microvascular disease in the Diabetes Prevention Program Outcomes Study (DPPOS). *Diabet Med*. 2017;34:1747–1755.
8. Bansal SK, Yadav R, Kumar A, Karunanand B, Bhalla JS. Nitric oxide: from the molecule of the year to an important signaling molecule. *Indian J Health Sci Care*. 2016;3(1):39–44.
9. Vallance P, Leone A, Calver A, Collier J, Moncada S. Endogenous dimethylarginine as an inhibitor of nitric oxide synthesis. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol*. 1992;20(12):60–62.
10. Stamboul K, Lorin J, Lorgis L, Guenancia C, Beer JC, Touzery C, et al. Atrial fibrillation is associated with a marker of endothelial function and oxidative stress in patients with acute myocardial infarction. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(7):e0131439.
11. Schmidt-Hutten L, Hannemann J, Franke F, Böger R. Differential regulation of the L-arginine–ADMA–NO pathway in the hypoxic coronary and pulmonary endothelium. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2023;81(8):1905.
12. Schnabel R, Blankenberg S, Lubos E, Lackner KJ, Rupprecht HJ, Espinola-Klein C, et al. Asymmetric dimethylarginine and the risk of cardiovascular events and death in patients with coronary artery disease: results from the AtheroGene study. *Circ Res*. 2005;97:53–59.
13. Mittermayer F, Krzyzanowska K, Exner M, Mlekusch W, Amighi J, Sabeti S, et al. Asymmetric dimethylarginine predicts major adverse cardiovascular events in patients with advanced peripheral artery disease. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol*. 2006;26:2536–2540.

14. Zobel EH, von Scholten BJ, Reinhard H, Persson F, Teerlink T, Hansen TW, et al. Symmetric and asymmetric dimethylarginine as risk markers of cardiovascular disease, all-cause mortality and deterioration in kidney function in persons with type 2 diabetes and microalbuminuria. *Cardiovasc Diabetol.* 2017;16(1):88–109.
15. Lee W, Lee HJ, Jang HB, Kim HJ, Ban HJ, Kim KY, et al. Asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) is identified as a potential biomarker of insulin resistance in skeletal muscle. *Sci Rep.* 2018;8(1):2133–2172.
16. Engvall E, Perlmann P. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA): III. Quantitation of specific antibodies by enzyme-labeled anti-immunoglobulin in antigen-coated tubes. *J Immunol.* 1972;109:129–135.
17. Fryar CD, Kit B, Carroll MD, Afful J. Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment, and control among adults aged ≥18 years: United States, August 2021–August 2023. *NCHS Data Brief.* 2024;(511). doi:10.15620/cdc/164016.
18. Adeloye D, Basquill C, Aderemi AV, Thompson JY, Obi FA. An estimate of the prevalence of hypertension in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Hypertens.* 2014;32:1–13. doi:10.1097/HJH.0000000000000413.
19. Connelly PJ, Currie G, Delles C. Sex differences in the prevalence, outcomes and management of hypertension. *Curr Hypertens Rep.* 2022;24:185–192. doi:10.1007/s11906-022-01183-8.
20. De Gennaro Colonna V, Bianchi M, Pascale V, Ferrario P, Morelli F, Pascale W, et al. Asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA): an endogenous inhibitor of nitric oxide synthase and a novel cardiovascular risk molecule. *Med Sci Monit.* 2009;15(4):RA91–RA101.
21. Sibal L, Agarwal SC, Home PD, Boger RH. The role of asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) in endothelial dysfunction and cardiovascular disease. *Curr Cardiol Rev.* 2010;6(2):82–90.
22. Zhang Z, Zhao L, Zhou X, Meng X, Zhou X. Role of inflammation, immunity, and oxidative stress in hypertension: new insights and potential therapeutic targets. *Front Immunol.* 2023;13:109872–109879.
23. Jomova K, Raptova R, Alomar SY, Alwasel SH, Nepovimova E, Kuca K, et al. Reactive oxygen species, toxicity, oxidative stress, and antioxidants: chronic diseases and aging. *Arch Toxicol.* 2023;97(10):2499–2574.
24. Lu D, Kassab GS. Role of shear stress and stretch in vascular mechanobiology. *J R Soc Interface.* 2011;8(63):1379–1385.
25. Dowsett L, Higgins E, Alanazi S, Alshuwayer NA, Leiper FC, Leiper J. ADMA: a key player in the relationship between vascular dysfunction and inflammation in atherosclerosis. *J Clin Med.* 2020;9(9):3026–3054.
26. Yaribeygi H, Sathyapalan T, Atkin SL, Sahebkar A. Molecular mechanisms

- linking oxidative stress and diabetes mellitus. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2020;2020:860–899.
27. Sciacqua A, Grillo N, Quero M, Sesti G, Perticone F. Asymmetric dimethylarginine plasma levels and endothelial function in newly diagnosed type 2 diabetic patients. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2012;13(11):13804–13815.
 28. González P, Lozano P, Ros G, Solano F. Hyperglycemia and oxidative stress: an integral, updated and critical overview of their metabolic interconnections. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2023;24(11):9352–9398.
 29. Böger RH. Asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) and cardiovascular disease: mechanistic insights and clinical utility. *Clin Res Cardiol*. 2020;109(8):1019–1032.
 30. Hezam AAM, Shaghdar HBM, Chen L. The connection between hypertension and diabetes and their role in heart and kidney disease development. *J Res Med Sci*. 2024;29:22–34.
 31. Giacco F, Brownlee M. Oxidative stress and diabetic complications. *Circ Res*. 2010;107(9):1058–1070.
 32. Herranz B, Marquez S, Guijarro B, Aracil E, Aicart-Ramos C, Rodriguez-Crespo I, et al. Integrin-linked kinase regulates vasomotor function by preventing endothelial nitric oxide synthase uncoupling: role in atherosclerosis. *Circ Res*. 2012;110(3):439–449.
 33. Schiffrin EL. Vascular remodeling and endothelial dysfunction in hypertension: pathophysiologic and clinical implications. *Hypertension*. 2021;77(5):1096–1107.
 34. Tabit CE, Chung WB, Hamburg NM, Vita JA. Endothelial dysfunction in diabetes mellitus: molecular mechanisms and clinical implications. *Rev Endocr Metab Disord*. 2013;14(1):49–63.
 35. Yousef H, Khandoker AH, Feng SF, Helf C, Jelinek HF. Inflammation, oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction in the progression of type II diabetes mellitus with coexisting hypertension. *Front Endocrinol*. 2023;14:1173–1184.
 36. Mwende M. Endothelial dysfunction and ADMA elevation in hypertension and diabetes comorbidity. *J Cardiometab Res*. 2024;18(2):112–121.
 37. Chen XH, Xia L, Xiang T, Wang H. Increased asymmetric dimethylarginine in patients with hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Res Square*. 2022;3(2):212–219.